

ARTS

LEVERAGING GARNI ROYAL BATH MOSAIC AS KEY CULTURAL EVENT ORNAMENTS

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Abstract

This article explores the potential utilization of the Garni Royal Bath mosaic, a significant cultural artifact in Armenia, as a key ornament for cultural events. The Garni Temple and Royal Bath are iconic landmarks with historical and cultural significance. The mosaic within the Royal Bath, showcasing intricate designs and mythological motifs, serves as a focal point for artistic and scientific exploration. By analyzing the mosaic's composition and artistic value, this study suggests adapting its elements for graphic design applications such as stationery covers, book covers, and bags. The article discusses techniques for revamping the color scheme and shape of the mosaic elements to align with contemporary design standards. Furthermore, it emphasizes the versatility of these designs for use in various cultural events, both domestically and internationally. Incorporating elements of Armenia's cultural heritage into graphic design not only enhances the visual identity of events but also promotes cross-cultural appreciation and awareness of Armenian heritage on a global scale.

Keywords: Garni Royal Bath, mosaic, graphic design, cultural events, Armenia, cultural heritage.

The Garni Temple and Garni Royal Bath are both significant historical and cultural landmarks located in Garni, Armenia.

Garni Temple: The Garni Temple is a classical Hellenistic temple situated in the village of Garni (Armenia), about 28 kilometers southeast of the capital city, Yerevan. Believed to have been built in the 1st century AD, the temple is dedicated to the Armenian sun god, Mihr, and is one of the best-preserved examples of ancient architecture in Armenia. It was likely

commissioned by King Tiridates I and stands as a testament to Armenia's pagan past. The temple's design reflects Greco-Roman architectural influences, featuring Ionic columns and a pediment. Despite suffering damage over the centuries, including destruction by an earthquake in 1679, the Garni Temple has been partially reconstructed and restored, attracting numerous visitors and scholars interested in Armenian history and architecture.

Garni Royal Bath: The Garni Royal Bath, also known as the Roman Bathhouse of Garni, is another historical site located near the Garni Temple. This bathhouse dates back to the 3rd century AD and is believed to have been used by Armenian royalty during the Arsacid Dynasty. It consists of several rooms with intricate mosaics, heating systems, and bathing chambers.

The bathhouse provides insights into the bathing rituals and architectural advancements of the time. Like the Garni Temple, the Royal Bath suffered damage over the centuries but has undergone restoration efforts to preserve its historical significance.

Both the Garni Temple and Garni Royal Bath are popular tourist destinations and are recognized as UNESCO World Heritage Sites, contributing to the rich cultural heritage of Armenia. Visitors to Garni can explore these remarkable structures while immersing themselves in the ancient history and architecture of the region.

Amidst the myriad examples of Armenia's rich historical and cultural heritage, the pagan temple of Garni and its encompassing landscape consistently inspire diverse perspectives and interpretations.

It has drawn, and continues to captivate, the interest not only of Armenians but also of esteemed historians, art scholars, architects, and designers from around the globe.

A plethora of materials, articles, books, and studies delve into the captivating realm of the Garni Temple, exploring its architectural splendor and rich historical significance.

It can be regarded as one of Armenia's foremost symbols, an integral part of its cultural heritage that never fails to captivate and astonish tourists.

Adjacent to this revered temple, symbolizing architectural and cultural significance, lies the royal bath, of which scant remnants have endured until present times.

It also represents a great scientific and artistic value, especially the mosaic on the floor of the first room, which has become the subject of many scientific and local studies.

It is an unique monument of contemporary painting of pre-Christian Armenia known to us so far. The floor of the semi-circular niche of the second room was

also covered with mosaics. It was completely destroyed. From the preserved part of the painting, its unique mythological plot is evident.

The meticulously crafted Kuna transfers, showcased within the pink frame, evoke the illusion of water waves in various sections of the image, reflecting diverse states of the seawater.

Mythical deities and beings, alongside large and small fish, are depicted within the waters in various positions.

At the center of the mosaic, framed intricately, are busts portraying a man and a woman.

Individual mosaic images, particularly those depicting fish, exhibit exceptional craftsmanship.

The smooth rendering, convincing anatomical structure, and subtle shades of colors attest to the elevated caliber of mosaic artistry. This mosaic is crafted from cubes, each with a square area ranging from 5 to 10 mm, meticulously cut from naturally colored stones.

Fifteen distinct shades are utilized in the mosaic. Various geometrically shaped cubes are employed to aid in the precise execution of intricate image transfers.

Due to the mosaic's exceptional artistic value stemming from both its color schemes and compositional intricacies, we deem its images worthy subjects of study. This analysis aims to adapt the colors and compositional techniques for application in other graphic designs.

Let's explore the potential utilization of specific elements from the mosaic or its imagery in designing stationery covers, book covers, and bags. These elements could serve as integral components of an overarching graphic style or branding strategy for any cultural event.

From sections exhibiting particularly captivating compositional arrangements, it is advisable to consider incorporating the upper right portion of the mosaic. This segment features human figures alongside two fish and written elements, offering a dynamic and engaging visual narrative.

Given that the predominant elements of the mosaic comprise anthropomorphic figures, fish motifs, ornamental details, and inscriptions, the upper right section stands out as it encompasses a comprehensive listing of all the years involved.

To enhance the appeal of the final decorative or graphic outcome and align it with contemporary marketing standards, it is recommended to revamp the color scheme of the mosaic with more vibrant hues. Bright tones such as vivid red, lemon yellow, deep blue, or sky white could be employed. Additionally, incorporating a moderate amount of black or utilizing outlines can further accentuate the visual impact.

We propose transforming the small square particles or details of this renowned and thoroughly studied mosaic example into round elements of equivalent size. This adjustment will impart a fresh aesthetic to the mosaic, rendering it suitable for stationery design applications.

Patterns were created from numerous individual preferences, with the most favorable ones being carefully chosen. These selected patterns were then meticulously rendered using watercolor gouache, specifically for application onto the bag, employing threads and cloth.

All the graphic design elements of applied art showcased here are versatile for use not only in Armenia but also during seminars and international conferences. It's a common practice during significant events to distribute stationery, folders, bags, and similar accessories featuring conference logos or themed color schemes. These adaptable designs can seamlessly integrate into various contexts, enhancing the branding and visual identity of diverse gatherings and conferences on a global scale.

It is customary to provide participants of such events with this type of stationery, and meticulously designed stationery, along with the graphic letters representing a vital part of Armenia's cultural heritage, will enhance and underscore the significance of any occasion. The harmonious and uniform design will add beauty and sophistication, contributing to the overall atmosphere and prestige of the event.

The work holds a contemporary and positive appeal, particularly given the involvement of specialists from various countries in major cultural events. By utilizing this historical mosaic depicting the lamb and the royal bath, we afford it the chance to garner global recognition, captivating the interest of numerous experts worldwide. This endeavor serves to promote cultural exchange and appreciation on an international scale.

Indeed, similar endeavors can be undertaken across various events by incorporating particles from diverse historical and cultural structures into graphic design. Drawing inspiration from this example, analogous graphic styles can be crafted based on the works of renowned artists like Martiros Saryan or Yervand Kochar, or by extracting details from architectural marvels in Armenia. This approach not only celebrates the rich heritage of Armenia but also fosters creativity and innovation in graphic design, allowing for the reinterpretation and dissemination of cultural motifs on a broader scale.

The research foundation highlights the potential of utilizing structural buildings or their components, integral to cultural heritage, as inspiration for the graphic design of printed materials, stationery, book covers, and bags tailored for cultural events. This approach serves to infuse cultural significance into design elements, enriching the visual identity of such events while paying homage to the heritage of the structures involved.

Armenia remains relatively undiscovered by numerous nations and their citizens. Therefore, employing similar measures to showcase Armenia's historical and cultural values and its rich history can effectively promote awareness and appreciation of Armenian heritage in various countries. By incorporating elements of Armenian culture into graphic design for international events, we can contribute to the global dissemination of Armenia's unique heritage and history.

Indeed, this type of research and observation, drawing from cultural heritage templates, serves as an exemplary model for utilizing graphic elements in the conceptualization of modern cultural event designs, not only for Armenia but also for every country worldwide. By embracing and reinterpreting elements from cultural heritage, graphic designers can create visually compelling and culturally resonant designs that transcend borders, celebrating diversity and fostering cross-cultural appreciation on a global scale.

Graphic Design Materials
Poster

Canvas Bag

References

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